

Studies on Pyrazolones. Part-III. Synthesis, Dyeing and Antifungal Activity of some 1-Substituted-3-phenyl-4-(2/4-carboxyphenylazo)-5-pyrazolones

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A series of new pyrazolones and esters have been synthesised. Treatment of ethyl benzoylacetate with diazotised 2/4-aminobenzoic acid gave ethyl 2-(2/4-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetates. Reaction of the esters with anilinomalonic acid hydrazides gave 1-substituted-3-phenyl-4-(2/4-carboxyphenylazo)-5-pyrazolones. The dyes impart mostly light yellow colour of different shades on cotton, silk and wool fibres and light orange to deep brown on nylon fibres in presence of mordants. The pyrazolones were tested for their antifungal activity.

In continuation of our work¹ and in view of the biological² activities associated with pyrazolones³, we report here the synthesis of two esters, ethyl 2-(2/4-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetates and 5-pyrazolones possessing 1,3-diketoaminoaryl moiety at 1-position and phenylazo at 4-position (Scheme 1) with the object of screening for their antifungal activities along with their value as dyes for fibres.

Scheme 1

Ethyl 2-(2-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetate (1a) and ethyl 2-(4-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetate (1b) obtained by condensing ethyl benzoylacetate

with diazotised 2/4-aminobenzoic acid on condensation with malonanilic acid hydrazides³ in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, gave the title compounds in 30–50% yields.

Experimental

Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. M.p.s. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Ethyl 2-(2-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetate (1a): 2-Aminobenzoic acid (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 6N HCl (25 ml) and cooled to -2° . Sodium nitrite solution cooled to -2° was then added to it dropwise followed by ethyl benzoylacetate (0.01 mol) and a suspension of sodium acetate (10 g) in ethanol (25 ml) maintaining a low temperature. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol as orange needles (2.04 g, 60.0%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 63.88; H, 4.62; N, 8.21. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₅ requires: C, 63.53; H, 4.70; N, 8.24%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1660 (C=O), 1580 (N=N) and 3080–3160 cm⁻¹ (OH).

Ethyl 2-(4-carboxyphenylazo)-2-benzoylacetate (1b): By following the above procedure, 4-aminobenzoic acid gave 1b as yellow crystals (2.75 g, 81.0%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 63.98; H, 4.59; N, 8.26. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₅ requires: C, 63.53; H, 4.70; N, 8.24%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1660 (C=O), 1590 (N=N) and 3080–3160 cm⁻¹ (OH).

1-Anilinomalonyl-3-phenyl-4-(2-carboxyphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone (2a): A mixture of malonanilic acid hydrazide³ (0.195 g, 0.001 mol), 1a (0.33 g, 0.001 mol) and glacial acetic acid (7 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid on crystallisation from aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1) afforded orange crystals (0.08 g, 17.05%), m.p. 295° . The aforementioned experiment when repeated using a drop of concentrated H₂SO₄ gave orange crystals (0.19 g,

40.05%), m.p. 295° (Found: C, 64.38; H, 4.73; N, 14.80. $C_{25}H_{19}N_5O_8$ requires: C, 63.96; H, 4.51; N, 14.49%); ν_{max} 1 690 (C=O), 1 585 (N=N) and 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Similarly, compounds 2b–j and 3a–j were prepared (Table 1).

Compd. no.	R ₁	Yield (%)		M.p. °C
		Without H ₂ SO ₄	In presence of H ₂ SO ₄	
		2a	H	
2b	2-Cl	12.9	52.6	290
2c	3-Cl	15.9	49.7	300
2d	4-Cl	23.8	49.7	286
2e	2-Me	12.4	43.4	291
2f	3-Me	13.4	47.6	295
2g	4-Me	17.5	45.5	291
2h	2-OMe	10.0	30.0	295
2i	3-OMe	15.0	24.0	220
2j	4-OMe	23.6	38.0	275
3a	H	21.3	47.5	310
3b	2-Cl	17.5	37.3	318
3c	3-Cl	14.9	49.3	310
3d	4-Cl	21.4	49.4	312
3e	2-Me	23.1	41.8	305
3f	3-Me	12.4	46.5	315
3g	4-Me	19.9	45.3	310
3h	2-OMe	25.4	35.3	215
3i	3-OMe	14.0	22.8	210
3j	4-OMe	43.2	50.1	312

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; colour of all compounds were light to deep orange, except 2h and 3h which were bright yellow.

Dyeing characteristics: Cotton, silk, wool and nylon fibres were used after thorough washing with cold and hot distilled water. A 1.0% solution of 2d, 2e, 2j, 3d, 3g or 3j was used and a 0.1% solution of CuSO₄, Na₂SO₄ or K₂Cr₂O₇ in glacial acetic acid was used as mordant. The fibres were soaked and kept for 1 h after moderate heating. The dyed fibres were washed with water and dried in air. Some of them were subjected to repeated washing with common soap and drying in air (3 times) along with exposure to sun-light in open air (6×3 h) and the fastness properties were determined by comparing

these fibres with the untreated/unexposed corresponding dyed fibres.

Results and Discussion

Compounds 2b, 2h, 2j, 3d and 3i were tested for their antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, *S. faecalis*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. aureus*, *C. neoformans*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *C. albicans* and *A. fumigatus*. Only 2j and 3d were found to be effective against the fungi *T. mentagrophytes* at minimum inhibitory concentration of 12.5 and 25.0 $\mu g ml^{-1}$, respectively. All other compounds tested were found ineffective upto concentration of 100 $\mu g ml^{-1}$.

The solubility of 2a–j and 3a–j was found high due to the presence of CO₂H group. Maximum stability of the shades imparted on different fibres was shown by 3d. The colours imparted were mostly yellow of different shades on cotton, silk and wool, and light orange to deep brown on nylon fibres.

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